

HARMLESS

**HARMLESS workshop on Safe-and- Sustainable-by-
Design (SSbD) for SMEs: Advanced Materials in
Product Development**

**25th May 2023, online
10:00 – 11:30h CEST**

HARMLESS

- Call for **Safe by design**, from science to regulation: **multi-component nanomaterials** (NMBP-16)
- Duration: **49 months** (Feb. '25)
- Consortium:
 - 20 Partners** from 12 EU countries
 - **2 Industries** (BASF, Nouryon)
 - **4 SMEs**
- Coordinators:
 - Tobias Stoeger, Otmar Schmid (Helmholtz Zentrum München, Germany)
- www.harmless-project.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953183.

Selected EU/OECD activities – Safe-and-Sustainable-by Design (SSbD)

European Green Deal

https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action/european-green-deal_en

- EU Action plan "Towards a Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil"
- Circular Economy Action Plan
- EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment

A **pre-market approach to chemicals** that focuses on providing a function (or service), while **avoiding volumes and chemical properties that may be harmful** to human health and the environment. (Def. of SSbD in CSS)

SSbD Framework by Joint Research Center (JRC, Ispra, Italy) – July 2022

<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC128591>

- Safe and Sustainable by Design chemical and material - Framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for **chemicals and materials**
- not a regulation or legislation, but is intended as a guidance to support or stimulate innovation
- 2-y Stakeholder consultation on "Application of the SSbD framework to case studies"

OECD Working Party on Manufactured Nanomat. – Steering Group on Advanced Materials (AdMa)

Advanced Materials (AdMa) are understood as materials that are rationally designed to have

- new or enhanced properties, and/or
 - targeted or enhanced structural features
- with the objective to achieve specific or improved functional performance (over conventional materials, CoMa)

Objectives

Introduction to HARMLESS
approach to Integration of
Safe-and-Sustainably-by-
Design (SDbD) principles in
AdMa-enhanced product
development

Make SSbD work for SMEs!

Agenda

25th May 2023, 10:00 - 11:30 CEST, online

10:00 - 10:05

Agenda and Objectives of the Workshop

by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

10:05 - 10:20

**Easy steps towards SSbD - Guidance for avoiding
"obvious" risks with nanomaterials**

by Michael Persson (CIT)

10:20 - 10:35

**Overview of HARMLESS SSbD framework and
Decision Support System**

by Blanca Suarez (TEMASOL) and Susan Dekkers (TNO)

10:35 - 10:50

**AI-based data acquisition tool & integration
into existing databases**

by Nina Jeliaskova (IDEA)

10:50 - 11:00

Wrap up & Q&A Session

Moderated by Otmar Schmid (HMGU)

11:00 - 11:30

**Q&A session for SMEs who want to
become involved in the project**

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Easy steps towards SSbD – Guidance for avoiding “obvious” risks with nanomaterials

Michael Persson

Senior Advisor Material at Chalmers Industriteknik (CIT), Sweden

Outline

- **My background (research institute-10y, large industry-30y, SME-2y)**
 - Advanced ceramics: submicron particles, metal oxide sols, whiskers
 - Paper industry: large volumes (colloidal silica) and high demands
 - Support SME's in process and product development
- **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)**
- **Why participating in nanosafety activities?**
- **Experiences and material properties**

Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD)

Safety: hazard x exposure = risk

Sustainability: nanomaterials if safe is an efficient tool for creating sustainable solutions (less raw material and energy used)

Why participating in nanosafety activities?

1. For a producer or user of nanomaterials:

- Innovation = Sustainability = Safety**
- Early warnings**

2. Amorphous silica is safe to use in recommended applications, but minor modifications may change the risks. New applications have new demands.

3. How to use the in-built safe-by-design aspects of colloidal silica (amorphous, water-based, soluble, irreversibly aggregation)?

HARMLESS Case Studies

- **Sector-specific approaches**, because industry sectors differ in *functionality and concern*, circularity, applicable regulation, intended use by professionals or by consumers, or in the environment.

CS 1 - Papermaking

Material: silica additives
Sector: manufacturing – accelerated dewatering

CS 2 - Paint formulations

Material: silica additives
Sector: construction – dirt repellent facades

CS 3 - Catalysts

Material: perovskites
Sector: automotive mobility – three-way-catalyst

La, Co, Ni, Pt, + Pd (~1%)

Focus of advanced case study materials

- **Mixtures of (rare earth) metals/oxides**
- **HARN (High Aspect Ratio Nanomaterials)**

SiO₂
HARN

CS 4 - Facade insulation

Material: aerogel fibre
Sector: construction – insulation

CS 5 - Agriculture

Material: modified imogolite multi-component nanotubes
Sector: agriculture – environmental plant protection

O, Si, C, Al, Mg, Zr, Cr, Fe, Co, S, Ca, Sn, Cu,* Au*
HARN

Inorganic nanotubes: Imogolites (Al, Si) (HARN)

Experiences and data are important

- A simple way of looking at Nanomaterials:
 1. Traditional/conventional nanomaterials
 2. Traditional materials produced as nanomaterials
 3. New nanomaterials (AdMa)

Even a minor modification may change the risk (↓ or ↑)

Material properties are important and may indicate potential risks

- Amorphous – crystalline phase(s)
- Spherical – High aspect ratio (fiberlike, HARN)
- Soluble – inert stable*
- Hydrophilic – hydrophobic
- Nonionic – anionic – cationic
- Liquid dispersions – dry powder**

*Toxic ions could be a potential problem

**Risk for inhalable dust

The Colloidal Silica example (silica nanoparticles)

- Reduction of exposure and hazard (toxicity)

Exposure

- | | |
|----------------------|--|
| 1. Production | closed wet process |
| 2. Shipping/handling | liquid dispersion |
| 3. Customer handling | wet handling |
| 4. End-of-life | Irreversible aggregation upon drying, will dissolve in water |

Hazard

Surface modification is an efficient tool to balance performance in application and Hazard (ex. silane modified silica).

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Overview of the HARMLESS SSbD framework

Blanca Suarez Merino (TEMAS Solutions)

25th May 2023

Why do we need a SSbD Approach

■ Nanomaterials/Advanced Materials

Toxicity is driven by:

- Intrinsic characteristics (phys-chem)
- System dependent toxicity within biological matrices (charge, cellular uptake)

- Toxicity is mainly surface area based (not mass based)
- Infinite testing combinations (testing one by one not feasible)
- Testing Guidelines not developed for this purpose

Ag NP (20 nm) in media without serum (TEM 97000x)

Ag NP (20 nm) in media with serum (TEM 97000x)

Opportunity to develop a Safe and Sustainable by Design Strategy

What SSbD is not...

Why SSbD is not only Risk Management

The Safe and Sustainable by Design Approach

The Safe and Sustainable by Design Approach

The Harmless SSbD Approach

Lack of data availability

Grouping Approaches

Tools

The HARMLESS SSbD concept is realised by the HARMLES SSbD Decision Support System

The Harmless SSbD Approach

SSbD Framework – Sustainability module

Dedicated questionnaires per innovation stage

- *Environmental Sustainability*
- *Sustainable use of natural resources*
- *Energy efficiency*
- *Pollution prevention*
- *Supply chain*
- *Circularity*

HARMLESS questionnaire inspired to fulfil the EU SSbD criteria

VS

From a SSbD Framework – To a Decision Support System

The realisation of the HARMLESS SSbD concept
into an applicable DSS

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HARMLESS Decision Support System

Susan Dekkers (TNO)

25th May 2023

Objectives

- Build a user-friendly Decision Support System (DSS)
- Based on SSbD Framework
- For complex HARNs and multi-component ENMs
- Using existing and newly generated data, methods and tools
- Integration of data and models
- Use insights from case-studies and stakeholder feedback

Based on the HARMLESS SSbD Framework

Innovation stages

Life cycle stages

Decision support approach

Using existing and newly generated data, methods and tools

Please perform the following actions to get the most accurate result

<h3>Advanced Material Early Assessment</h3> <p>LICARA nanoScan allows a preliminary but swift assessment of benefits and risks for nano products. This is an excellent Tier-1 tool to start with to gain a simple but broad early view of hazard, exposure and sustainability.</p> <p>Attach existing run > Start scan run ></p>			
<h3>Nano Exposure Quantifier (NEQ)</h3> <p>Stoffenmanager & NEQ via bayesian network</p> <p>Start scan run ></p>			

Decision support approach & visualisation

Based on Risk Informed Decision Making

Safety and sustainability aspects	Product idea & screening	Lab Scale	Pilot Scale
	Production & manufacturing	Production & manufacturing	Production & manufacturing
Occupational safety	OK	OK	Warning
Environmental safety	OK	Warning	OK
Climate change	OK	OK	OK
Resource use and circularity	OK	Alert	Warning
Pollution prevention	OK	OK	Alert
Ethical suppliers	Alert	Warning	Alert
	Use	Use	Use
Consumer safety	OK	OK	OK
Environmental safety	OK	Alert	Alert
Climate change	OK	Warning	Warning
Resource use and circularity	OK	OK	Alert
Pollution prevention	OK	OK	OK
Benefits	OK	OK	Warning
	End of life	End of life	End of life
Occupational safety	OK	OK	OK
Environmental safety	Warning	Warning	Alert
Climate change	OK	Warning	Warning
Resource use and circularity	OK	OK	Alert
Pollution prevention	OK	OK	OK

- **OK** Ready to go to next phase
- **Warning** There are concerns that require attention
- **Alert** There are major concerns blocking progression

Key points of the decision support approach

- Easy to use
- Follow innovation stages
- From limited to more comprehensive data and methods
- Including uncertainty
- Integration of data and knowledge
 - To reduce amount of questions
 - To reduce the uncertainty
 - For similarity assessment and read across
- **This all stands or falls with data availability**

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AI-based data acquisition tool & integration into existing databases

**HARMLESS workshop on Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) for SMEs:
Advanced Materials in Product Development**

Nina Jeliaskova, Ideacosult Ltd., Sofia, BG

Introduction

- **Databases**
 - Focus: Nanosafety Data Interface to eNanoMapper databases
 - Other data sources;
 - REACH dossiers, chemical structure databases, material databases
- **Challenge - How do we find data relevant to a new material ?**
 - What materials are related to a new material ?
 - What data (might) be relevant?

Nanosafety Data Interface

Online user interface enabling user-friendly access to the aggregated search index of the (sub)set of eNanoMapper database instances. Usually, the user interface is project specific and protected but can also be publicly available. (Multiple project specific interfaces are at [https://search.data.enanomapper.net/.](https://search.data.enanomapper.net/))

eNanoMapper data model

A set of data elements and relationships that represents chemical substances with a complex composition and associated experimental data, extended to NMs by the EU-funded project eNanoMapper (<http://www.enanomapper.net/>).

eNanoMapper database instance

An installation of AMBIT software (<http://ambit.sf.net>), which implements the eNanoMapper data model. Usually consists of data from individual nanosafety projects and may be protected by role-based access to keep data confidential.

Jeliazkova N, ..., Nymark P. **Towards FAIR Nanosafety Data.** *Nature Nanotechnology.* May 2021, doi:s41565-021-00911-6

Dashboard – data availability

Dashboard –visual summaries

Composition dashboard

Dashboard – material fingerprints

study_type Particle size distribution (Granulometry) ▾

Physchem characterisation

Composition

Functionality : AI based data acquisition (example)

Add material names or description

≡ Graphene oxide (NH₂-functionalized)

≡ GRAPHENE OXIDE (PRISTINE)

≡ JRCNM01000a titanium dioxide nanoparticle

≡ OPTIMAT® 2550

Details (AI extracted)

material	Material class	Functionality	Product class	Benefits	Particles/Fibres/Platelets	Nano?
Graphene oxide (NH ₂ -functionalized)	2D nanomaterial	Adsorption, sensing, catalysis	Polymer composites, coating	High surface area, high electrical conductivity	Platelets	nanomaterial
Graphene oxide (PRISTINE)	Nanomaterial	Conductive, barrier, adsorption	Electronics, energy storage, sensors	High electrical conductivity, high surface area	Particles	nanomaterial
JRCNM01000a titanium dioxide nanoparticle	Titanium dioxide nanoparticle	UV protection, whitening, anti-static	Cosmetics, paints, coatings, pigments	Improved UV protection, whitening	Particles	nanomaterial
OPTIMAT® 2550 Alumino Silicate	Inorganic	Adsorbent	Polymer, paint, coating, adhesive	High adsorption capacity, low toxicity	Particles	nanoenabled

Classes of materials (AI augmented descriptions)

The screenshot shows the HARMLESS eNanoMapper database interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, Project, Search, FAIR Tools Guide, Template Wizard, Help, and a user ID [n10705013] with a Log out button. The main heading is 'H2020 HARMLESS - eNanoMapper database'. Below this, there are filter controls: 'Filters Active - 1', 'Collapse All', 'Show All', and 'Clear All'. The search results are organized into three columns: 'Class', 'Subclass', and 'Advanced'. The 'Class' column lists 'metamaterials', 'paints', 'particle-filled composites', 'pigments', 'plastics' (highlighted), and 'rubber'. The 'Subclass' column lists 'biobased plastics', 'biodegrading plastics', 'plastics', 'recyclable plastics', and 'traceable plastics'. The 'Advanced' column shows 'false' and 'true'. Below the search results, there are buttons for 'Copy', 'Excel', 'CSV', 'PDF', and 'Print'. A search bar is located at the bottom right. The main content area displays details for 'plastics' and 'biobased plastics', including their definitions, compositions, functionalities, properties, and applications.

Class

- metamaterials
- paints
- particle-filled composites
- pigments
- plastics**
- rubber

Subclass

- biobased plastics
- biodegrading plastics
- plastics
- recyclable plastics
- traceable plastics

Advanced

- false
- true

Class/Subclass

Details

plastics

biobased plastics

Definition: Biobased plastics are plastics made from renewable resources such as plants, rather than from petroleum-based sources. They are typically biodegradable and compostable, and are often used in packaging and other consumer products.

Composition: Biobased plastics are typically composed of polylactic acid (PLA), polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), polycaprolactone (PCL), polybutylene succinate (PBS), and polyethylene furanoate (PEF).

Functionality: Biobased plastics are plastics made from renewable resources such as corn, sugarcane, and other plant-based materials. They are designed to be biodegradable and compostable, and can be used in a variety of applications, including packaging, food containers, and other consumer products. Biobased plastics are also more sustainable than traditional petroleum-based plastics, as they are made from renewable resources and can be recycled or composted at the end of their life cycle.

Properties: undefined

Applications: Biobased plastics have a wide range of applications, including packaging, automotive parts, medical devices, and consumer products. They can also be used in the construction of buildings and infrastructure, as well as in the production of textiles and fabrics. Additionally, biobased

<https://search.data.enanomapper.net/projects/harmless/adma/products/>

Find all materials of class of interest ; search in combined databases ; predict properties for the new and existing materials (next slide)

HARMLESS Home Project Search FAIR Tools Guide Template Wizard Help [n10705013] Log out

H2020 HARMLESS - eNanoMapper database

About NANOREG | NANOREG2 | CALIBRATE | CANANOLAB | SANOWORK | OMICS | PATROLS | HARMLESS |

Class: fillers (4), particle-filled composites (1)

Subclass: advanced fillers for materials with Ag wires (1), advanced fillers for materials with graphene (1), advanced fillers for materials with MWCNT (1), advanced fillers for materials with SWCNT (1), flexible display electrode materials (1)

Advanced: true (5)

Search: graphene

Classes of materials (AI augmented descriptions)

Copy Excel CSV PDF Print

Class/Subclass	Details
fillers	Definition: Advanced fillers for materials with SWCNTs are materials that are added to a base material to improve its properties, such as strength, electrical conductivity, thermal conductivity, and chemical resistance. Examples of advanced fillers for materials with SWCNTs include graphene, carbon nanotubes, and metal oxides. Composition: Advanced fillers for materials with SWCNTs can include graphene, carbon nanotubes, nanodiamonds, nanoclays, and nanofibers. Functionality: Advanced fillers with SWCNTs can be used to improve the mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties of materials. They can also be used to increase the strength and stiffness of materials, reduce their weight, and improve their electrical and thermal conductivity. Additionally, they can be used to reduce the cost of materials and increase their durability. Properties: undefined Applications: Advanced fillers with SWCNT can be used to improve the mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties of materials. They can be used to reinforce polymers, improve the electrical conductivity of composites, and increase the thermal conductivity of materials. They can also be used to reduce the weight of materials, improve the wear resistance of materials, and reduce the cost of production.
advanced fillers for materials with SWCNT	

Datamaps, based on multiple properties, composition, and combined REACH dossiers (small dots) and enanomapper database (large dots).

... predict properties for the new and existing materials (functionalized graphene oxide for demonstration purposes)

Predicted physchem property ranges (red-high, blue low)

Datamaps, based on multiple properties, composition, and combined REACH dossiers and enanomapper database

Predicted (eco)tox property ranges (red – high, blue low)

ECHA REACH dossiers (non-confidential)

- an important source of information on already registered substances.
- <https://echa.europa.eu/information-on-chemicals>
- free download in IUCLID6 format at (updated every 6 months) <https://iuclid6.echa.europa.eu/reach-study-results>.
- IDEA has an existing workflow of converting the IUCLID6 files and making them available in eNanoMapper compatible database
 - the LRI AMBIT tool, at <https://ambitlri.ideaconsult.net>

IUC Substance name: Reaction Mass Of 1,1'-Oxybis(Ethylbenzene) And Styrene, Oligomers
IUC Substance UUID: IUC6-d076f2ac-0c53-4823-908c-f98ae6227981
IUC Public name: Styrene Heavy Ends
Legal entity:
Legal entity UUID:
Type substance composition: multi-constituent substance/organic
IUC Substance Reference Identifier
 CAS: 916-736-9
 EC: 916-736-9
 Chemical name: reaction mass of 1,1'-oxybis(ethylbenzene) and styrene, oligomers,unnamed
 IUPAC name:
 UUID:
 IUC Flags:

Composition name: Reaction Mass Of 1,1'-Oxybis(Ethylbenzene) And Styrene, Oligomers
Composition UUID: L6-86565222-7e12-4b13-8329-b9d4e231a0d8
Purity of IUC Substance:

Type	Name	EC No.	CAS No.	Typical concentration	Concentration ranges	Structure
Constituent	1,1'-Oxybis(Ethylbenzene),Unnamed	272-620-1	68900-67-4	0 % (w/w)	0 % (w/w) - 0 % (w/w)	
Constituent	Styrene, Oligomers,Unnamed	500-008-9	9003-53-6	0 % (w/w)	0 % (w/w) - 0 % (w/w)	

Screenshot of a styrene substance in the eNanoMapper data model, with composition (top) and selected toxicity data (bottom)

Styrene Heavy Ends

7.2.1 Acute toxicity - oral (2)

Species	Endpoint	Value	Sex	Interpre of the results	Guideline	Study year	Owr	Reliability	UUID
-	LD50	(300, 2000) mg/kg bw	not specified	-		2014	-	2 (reliable with restrictions)	IUC6-E
rat	LD50	> 2000 mg/kg bw	female	-	OECD Guideline 423 (Acute Oral toxicity - Acute Toxic Class Method)	2015	-	1 (reliable without restriction)	IUC6-E

Showing 2 substance(s) (1 to 2) ◀ Previous Next ▶

Data maps (REACH dossiers)

• mono-constituent substance • not_specified • UVCB • multi-constituent substance
 • polymer

• organic • not_specified • inorganic • organometallic • petroleum product
 • element

Black: inorganic
Cyan: organic
Magenta: petroleum products
Red: organometallic
Gray: not specified

Black: mono-constituent
Cyan: multi-constituent
Magenta: UVCB
Gray: not specified

- Substance similarity by multiple properties
- Similar substances = close points

Substance similarity search (based on data maps)

Porous Silica 100nm-CuO doping-me NRCWE#070

Selected substance

(0.57) Porous Silica 300nm-CuO dop

Selected similar substance

NPO_1373 caLIBRate	NPO_1373 caLIBRate	NPO_1373 caLIBRate	NPO_1544
Porous Silica 300nm-CuO doping-me NRCWE#069	Porous Silica 100nm-CuO doping-me NRCWE#070	Non-porous Silica 300nm-CuO doping-me NRCWE#070 nanoparti	

Choose... ▾

- Choose...
- Phys-chem similarity
- Size similarity
- Surface area similarity
- Zeta potential similarity
- Radical Formation Potential
- Cell viability similarity
- Ecotox similarity**
- All properties similarity

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Page

NPO_1373 caLIBRate	CHEBI_59999
(0.57) Porous Silica 300nm-CuO doping-me NRCWE#069	control

(0.53) NM-401 MWCNT 64.2 nm JRCNM04001a	(0.53) control_NERC	(0.53) NM-400 MWCNT 13.6 nm JRCNM04000a	(0.52) Porous Silica 300nm-Me NRCWE#065	(0.55) Copper dinitrate 3251-23-8
		NPO_354 NANoREG	NPO_1373 caLIBRate	NPO_1892 NANoREG
				(0.52) Ag 16.7 nm NM-300K

Reference	Protocol	Endpoint	Result	Concentration	Treatment	replicate	Provided by
	OECD TG 474	FREQUENCY OF MICRONUCLEATED CELLS (MNC) IN NORMOCHROMATIC ERYTH	5.1667 MNCs/1000 NCEs (SD 2.0344)	4.7 ug/mouse	sample	-	
	DISPERSION MEDIUM: n.a. Delay between the last exposure and the sacrifice: 28 day Species: Mouse (C57BL/6J B6;129) female	PROPORTION OF POLYCHROMATIC ERYTHROCYTES (PCES) AMONG TOTAL ERY	19.8333 PCES/500 erythrocytes (SD 2.0344)	4.7 ug/mouse	sample	-	
FlOH In_vivo_toxicity_NH18-01_MN1_Gamma_Histopathology_FlOH_BATCH1 Sheet: Micronuclei (2018) This experiment Related experiments	E.exposure_frequency: 1 Method: AO organ: Blood SOP reference: link Exposure conditions: Pulmonary Number of exposure: Single injection Operator: KAJ	FREQUENCY OF MICRONUCLEATED CELLS (MNC) IN NORMOCHROMATIC ERYTH	4.8571 MNCs/1000 NCEs (SD 0.833)	14 ug/mouse	sample	-	FlOH
		PROPORTION OF POLYCHROMATIC ERYTHROCYTES (PCES) AMONG	17.8571 PCES/500 erythrocytes	14 ug/mouse	sample	-	

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Wrap up

Safe-and- Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) for SMEs: Advanced Materials in Product Development

Identified 32 Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs, MoA)

- 25 human health
- 7 ecotoxicology

37 New Approach Methods (NAMs) are developed – different TIER levels (*in vitro*, *in silico*)

- Hazard
- Exposure
- Internal dose
- Life Cycle Analysis
- Ecotoxicology

Safety & Sustainability assessment

- Datahub for multi-scale modelling (e.g. QSARs, AI-driven approaches)
- *In vitro* / *in vivo* / human translation (internal dose)
- „Positioning“ of AdMa in risk and sustainability matrix

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Q & A - Discussion - Get involved

**Safe-and- Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) for SMEs: Advanced
Materials in Product Development**

HOUSEKEEPING RULES

**Thank you for accepting
these rules that shall
ensure a smooth running
of the workshop!**

- Please use a headset and mute your microphone if you are not speaking.
- Please deactivate your camera if you are not talking.
- Questions
 - Please raise your hand if you want to say something.
 - OR use Chat: Start with typing “?”.
Based on the entries in the chat the moderator will pick up questions for further discussion within the group.

Get it touch with us – www.harmless-project.eu

CONTACT

Get in touch.

Any questions about our work or new ideas to contribute?
We'd love to hear about it.

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